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Building data models and data sharing. Purpose, approaches, and a case study on explainable demand response

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Building data models and data sharing. Purpose, approaches, and a case study on explainable demand response.

Nikos Sakkas, Christina Chaniotaki, Nikitas Sakkas

Apintech Ltd., Spatharikou 5 Str., 4004 Limassol, Cyprus

Email: info@apintech.com

Abstract. There are several approaches to building data modelling and there is a well-established rationale for the various related standards emerging in the area. In this work we acknowledge the importance of these approaches but also discuss their limitations. To this extent we draw the line between open data and open sharing and discuss its relevance. We also introduce a case study of a demand response application integrated with a XAI (explainable artificial intelligence) demand forecasting and we use it to practically highlight how open data and open sharing features interplay and integrate. We also discuss how open building model design will need to develop, so as to account for vital, in some cases, explainability information.

1. Introduction

The 4th Industrial Revolution is underpinned by sharing and collaboration approaches. These are more and more entering the mainstream and gradually putting aside the proprietary mindset and models of the past. Other paragraphs are indented (BodytextIndented style).

Data sharing is a long-established practice. There are several general-purpose cloud platforms (Google, Dropbox, etc.) as well as more specialized sharing services such as, for example, those provided by xenodo, OSF (Open Science Foundation) which focus on scientific data sharing. Finally, there are also sharing platforms that specialize in building applications (for example the Odyssey-Mure database in the EU, the "building datasets" from the Department of Energy in the USA).

The purpose of real-time data sharing would be multifold and could create value for both the research as well as the business community. For example, it could empower data-intensive and driven applications developed by third parties. It could also provide for factual and data-driven validation of new building-related products and services as well as data-driven benchmarking services. With more data available than ever before the industry is presented with a new challenge [8]. Device data is stored and communicated in many different formats. It has inconsistent, non-standard naming conventions, and provides very limited descriptors to enable us to understand its meaning. Simply put, the operational data from smart devices and equipment systems lacks information to describe its own meaning. As a result, data from today's devices, while technically

“available”, is hard to use, thus limiting the ability for building operators to fully benefit from the value contained in it. That is exactly where open data comes to our assistance.

Openness is key in unlocking these new opportunities. Openness can relate to either the data itself or the access to it. In the following, we will discuss the standards driven approaches (e.g. Brick, Haystack, BIM/IFC) for data sharing and will also review the subtle difference between open data and open sharing and consider their respective advantages and disadvantages.

We will also illustrate these ideas in the light of an explainable demand response case study, built on open access technology.

2. Open data or open access?

To understand what open data means, it is useful to think of the web and the HTML standard. An HTML document is self-explanatory to any browser. It “talks” a well-defined language that any browser can decipher and understand. HTML is a common language, and it is also a publicly available language. These two conditions are what essentially define open data.

Similarly, an open model for building data would require the development of a common language to describe building data and, of course, this common description would need to be made publicly available for all building-related applications to use.

In appreciation of the benefits of openness, there is intense ongoing activity in the construction industry to provide such open models. Below, we briefly review three of these models, which we consider the most dominant, though far from the only ones.

Haystack [7], uses a tagging system to capture the architecture of a BMS (Building Management System). Using tags, Haystack maps physical objects to entities. These entities can be abstractions for sites (buildings with addresses), pieces of equipment (e.g. an HVAC unit), or single points (e.g. a temperature sensor). These (site, equipment, point) are the three hierarchical tags used for entity definition within Haystack. After setting an entity tag to an object, every other tag assigned defines an attribute of the entity or links it to a different entity. Haystack can also capture relationships between sensors, pieces of equipment and sites; however, it does not capture any spatial information.

Brick [2], much like Haystack, uses tags to capture the architecture of a BMS system. While Haystack-based representations usually consist of ad-hoc collections of tags, leading to inconsistent modeling across sites, Brick tries to augment its tags with semantic rules, promoting both interpretability and consistency. Brick enriches tags with an underlying ontology, providing a framework to create the hierarchies and relationships necessary for describing building metadata. With an ontology, metadata can be analyzed using standard tools, and restrictions that prohibit arbitrary tag combinations can be placed (e.g. temperature sensors’ units can be restricted to Fahrenheit and Celsius). The concept of tagsets is introduced, which groups relevant tags in order to represent different entities. With Haystack, entities are defined by their individual tags, so their properties and relationships with other entities can only be specified at the tag level. With tagsets, we can have a cohesive concept of, for example, a temperature sensor. Tagsets also support the introduction of hierarchies – a zone temperature sensor is a subclass of a generic temperature sensor, and automatically inherits all of its properties.

Brick and Haystack include no geometry-related building information. They are essentially designed with BMS and operational building data in mind, and not CAD-like building design applications. If the data one needs to access includes these types of descriptions, then the only option is the BIM/IFC protocol. BIM stands for Building Information Modeling. Every BIM software has its own BIM implementation. So BIM cannot by itself be classified as open data. This is where IFC

(Industry Foundation Classes) comes in Vieira [11]. IFC offers a platform-neutral format of the BIM files (that can be read and edited by any BIM software). IFC is an open international standard (ISO 16739-1:2018)¹ and promotes vendor-neutral (or so-called agnostic) and usable capabilities across a wide range of devices and software apps. Thus, IFC is truly about open data.

The following figure illustrates the typical applicability of these three key standards with regard to the building lifecycle.

Figure 1. Building data standards applicability across the building lifecycle.

It is also noteworthy that there are more and more efforts to move beyond the current fragmentation and converge to a common standard [5], [6], something that would undoubtedly change the building data landscape and lead to greater adoption rates by the industry. Now, if one implements one of the above open data approaches, he has made a decisive step towards making his data available to third-party apps that “speak” the language. However, is this the only way to achieve data exchange?

Fortunately, the answer is no. Open data allows open access, but open access does not necessarily require open data. How, then, can closed and proprietary data allow open access? Data owners can do so if they publish a data access API (application programming interface). This API will allow any third party to get hold of the data regardless of their internal structure. Thus, with an open API the owner of the data can achieve the same goal: allow access to her data, or equivalently share her data for the use of humans or third-party apps.

One may ask which is the superior approach? Open data or open access, as defined above? Technically, the advantage lies by far with open data. Going back to our web paradigm at the beginning, simple open access (with no open-HTML data) would mean that you would have to implement the file public API to understand what it is about. In other words, you would be able to read the file, but it would be a nightmare having to implement proprietary APIs every time to figure out what is inside. Clearly, the web would have no chance at all if built only on open access and not open-HTML structured-data.

Alas, in the building industry things are vastly different. There are huge numbers of existing proprietary systems of all types that speak no standard language at all, and for which there is no evidence that they will adopt any of the main standards any time soon. For this vast proprietary ecosystem, providing for open data might be difficult or outright impossible. In any case, it is far more difficult than turning a proprietary file into HTML. The above web analogue has some conceptual value but can be very misleading if mechanically applied in a building data scope. Open access, however, may still present a convenient opportunity. Developing a public API allowing

¹ www.iso.org/standard/70303.html

access to your building data may be a viable option, perhaps even the only viable option, for data sharing and collaboration with third-party apps. Thus, we argue that open access is an important and promising approach in the domain of building data, a sphere where it is not realistic to expect anything as pervasive as the HTML standard to emerge in the foreseeable future.

Thus, in the building domain open data cannot be the sole approach towards data sharing. Open, API-based access is also a necessary complement to allow virtually any building-related proprietary data model to share its data, enabling it to enter the ecosystem of shareable data and take advantage of the associated collaborative business models.

Of course, there is no reason why this open-access API should not also be compliant with some of the discussed standards and benefit from both worlds: open data and open access. The best possible approach is a public data-sharing API that is also Brick/Haystack compliant for the BMS-like subdomain, and BIM/IFC for the CAD-like subdomain.

Below we will shift our attention to some emerging concepts such as explainability and discuss how these will impact our open data/open access discussion.

3. Explainability and building data models

Explainability is an emerging concept in artificial intelligence (AI). AI and advanced techniques such as neural networks, although well-known and appreciated for their superior prediction capacity come with a black box structure that does not allow drawing correct inferences about the underlying data. This often results in a feeling of uncertainty and/or risk. This is the point that explainability seeks to address. Its importance is directly proportional to the uncertainty and risk that comes with the AI model. In low-risk scenarios it may be of little importance. Indeed, if a model is recommending movies to watch, or if it generates your favourite colour, then the interpretability of the model could represent an overkill.

Explainability in principle comes in two packages; global and local. Global explainability is about the explanation of the model as a whole. Local explainability refers to the ability to investigate and understand why a particular model decision was reached, even if the model remains incomprehensible in its operation.

4. Explainability and building data models

We have published some results where we deploy local explainability and counterfactual based approaches in the case of country level energy forecasting for residences [10] and industry [9].

This work highlighted some new requirements for building models and related approaches described above. As an example, we find it necessary to include the notion of an “actionable” tag property, which defines whether the user has the ability to act upon the underlying tag. For instance, weather data is clearly and always non-actionable. Indoor temperature is typically actionable as one may act upon it via the thermostat settings; if such action is, however, for any reason not possible (e.g, because a fully automatic comfort control system is in place disallowing any user from interacting with it) then this data is non-actionable.

This piece of information is key for XAI and especially counterfactual driven investigations. Also, it is clearly the responsibility of the building data model to communicate this information and not the responsibility of any application to infer it. Just as it is necessary for the data to communicate its unit of temperature, whether it is Celsius or Fahrenheit. Hence, the need to model this property in the open building data model itself.

5. Model explainability and building models; the case of demand response

Below, we discuss a different application area, a case study in the area of building level demand response schemes and how it interplays with our open data and open access considerations.

Demand response is the capacity of end-use customers to change their electricity (or energy, more generally) usage from their normal or current consumption patterns in response to market signals. In contrast to energy efficiency, which aims at reducing the overall energy consumption, demand response is mainly about shifting consumption to a different point in time. Customers' participation in such schemes is of course voluntary. Demand response is a distinct and important functionality of the evolving smart grids. Its impact in allowing to expand renewable generation and more generally to optimize the use of the electric grid is well acknowledged. However there is one major factor that has not enabled demand response schemes to massively proliferate: consumer risk. A position paper published by Eurelectic [4] besides confirming the massive benefits that would come with a wider use of demand response, also draws attention to the inherent risk of these schemes, and how this negatively affects their uptake. Here is how this report explicitly states "Nevertheless, there is a key challenge to overcome in order to make such demand response offers available and sufficiently attractive for consumers: Lack of awareness of risks & benefits. Consumers can be interested in dynamic pricing if they are well informed and if the schemes are designed in an easy-to-use way to make savings in the bill achievable. Without information about their level of exposure to price volatility, i.e. knowing when electricity prices increase, consumers may potentially face significant increases in their bills during certain months". Similar concerns are reported also by Dutta et al [3].

Artificial intelligence is massively used in demand response approaches. A recent summary is provided by Antonopoulos et al [1] who report an exponential increase in the related work during the last 10 years. Reviewed papers on the topic were in the period 2010- 2012 about 2 to 3 on a yearly basis. This figure has now increased to about 40.

Our main approach in this work is to foster the need and pertinence of explainability when it comes to demand response. Something fully justified by the prominence of customer risk in demand response schemes for all related customers and therefore by the need to successfully mitigate it if such schemes are to take off to their full potential.

We are currently designing a building demand response controller, one that will foster advanced explainability features and will in this way counteract consumer risk, a main factor impeding a more drastic uptake of such schemes. Operational insight into this controller can be gained by investigating its entity- relationship schema.²

We will also be connecting the controller to a real time monitoring technology (WT).³ Incidentally, WT, typical of the industry case, does not implement any open data model. In addition, our ambition is to have this DR controller not restricted to some specific provider, i.e., allow it to work against any possible data model. Thus, we need to provide API based, open access and connectivity to get the data in the demand controller environment, along with what has been presented in paragraph 2 above.

This API based, open access, connectivity has been implemented.⁴ Any provider (such as our WT) may log in and export his real time data, by using the public API. Any third party (such as our

² www.figma.com/file/1cdmL77SmWHOVX5iiqDpBD/DP---ER-Diagram?node-id=0%3A1

³ www.wirelessthings.biz

⁴ ds.leiminte.com

demand response controller) may log-in and read the required real time data, by again using the public API. Documentation of this API is available.⁵

The DR controller relies on real time data to implement AI based forecasting based on a number of techniques: We are currently experimenting with structured time series, as well as ANNs based on public Tensorflow libraries.⁶ We are however also using an alternative and explainable AI approach based on genetic programming (GP) and symbolic expressions.

The following figure illustrates all three components in action: The BMS data provider (WT), the open access provider (DS) and the data consumer (explainable demand response app).

Figure 2. Open Data access.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

We have suggested above that open building models will benefit if they port their attention also to emerging explainability concepts, some of which (such as the actionability tag discussed above in the case of local explainability and counterfactual analysis) refer to building attributes, and therefore the building models themselves.

In any case, we have argued above that there is currently still little evidence that open building models are becoming mainstream in the industry. Such a convergence would be most welcome evidence in this direction is rather mixed and still inconclusive. In the current circumstance, we have argued that to provide for a truly open solution one cannot rely on the largely non existing open models but needs to provide for an open access API. This has been our approach for our demand response controller and its data access API presented above.

We also look forward embedding explainability in this controller as well as investigating the possible trade-off between accuracy and explainability i.e., what do we lose in terms of the typically high ANN forecasting accuracy when opting for a more explainable genetic programming (GP) based approach. Whether this model level explainability, will, similarly to the local explainability

⁵ ds.leiminte.com/api/documentation

⁶ tensorflow.org

case also require some accommodation at the level of the data model is currently under investigation.

7. Acknowledgements

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References

- [1] Ioannis Antonopoulos, Valentin Robu, Benoit Couraud, and David Flynn. Data-driven modelling of energy demand response behaviour based on a large-scale residential trial. *Energy and AI*, 4:100071, 2021.
- [2] Bharathan Balaji, Arka Bhattacharya, Gabriel Fierro, Jingkun Gao, Joshua Gluck, Dezhi Hong, Aslak Johansen, Jason Koh, Joern Ploennigs, Yuvraj Agarwal, et al. Brick: Metadata schema for portable smart building applications. *Applied energy*, 226:1273–1292, 2018.
- [3] Goutam Dutta and Krishnendranath Mitra. A literature review on dynamic pricing of electricity. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 68(10):1131–1145, 2017.
- [4] Eurelectric. Everything you always wanted to know about demand response.
- [5] Gabe Fierro, Jason Koh, Yuvraj Agarwal, Rajesh K Gupta, and David E Culler. Beyond a house of sticks: Formalizing metadata tags with brick. In *Proceedings of the 6th ACM International Conference on Systems for Energy-Efficient Buildings, Cities, and Transportation*, pages 125–134, 2019.
- [6] Gabe Fierro, Anand Krishnan Prakash, Cory Mosiman, Marco Pritoni, Paul Raftery, Michael Wetter, and David E Culler. Shepherding metadata through the building lifecycle. In *Proceedings of the 7th ACM International Conference on Systems for Energy-Efficient Buildings, Cities, and Transportation*, pages 70–79, 2020.
- [7] David R Karger, Karun Bakshi, David Huynh, Dennis Quan, and Vineet Sinha. Haystack: A customizable general-purpose information management tool for end users of semistructured data. In *Proc. of the CIDR Conf*, 2005.
- [8] DNES Prairie, MKG Samy, J Petze, and M Petock. Project-haystack-a caba white paper, 2016.
- [9] Nikos Sakkas and Nagia Athanasiou. Drivers of and counterfactuals for the final energy and electricity consumption in eu industry. *Academia Letters*, 2021.
- [10] Nikos Sakkas, Sofia Yfanti, Costas Daskalakis, Eduard Barbu, and Marharyta Domnich. Interpretable forecasting of energy demand in the residential sector. *Energies*, 14(20), 2021.
- [11] Renato Vieira, Paulo Carreira, Pedro Domingues, and Antonio Aguiar Costa. Supporting building automation systems in bim/ifc: reviewing the existing information gap. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 2020.